

Effects of Teaching Aids on Achievement in Concept Hydrocarbon among Secondary School Chemistry Students Iin Katsina State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Teaching Aids on Achievement in Hydrocarbon on concepts among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina State, Nigeria.” Three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically 3×2 pretest posttest factorial design was adopted for the study. The experimental groups were subjected to treatment using teaching aids (charts and models) while the control group were taught without teaching aids (charts nor models). The population of the consists of all government secondary school class two (SSII) chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. Sample size of 218, (Male 124 and Female 94) chemistry students were selected from target population using purposive sampling technique. Chemistry Achievement Test was used to collect data. The CAT was validated by experts from the Department of Science Education Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina state. Hence, a pilot study was conducted on the instrument and reliability coefficient of 0.64 was obtained using test-retest method. The data collected was analyzed using ANCOVA. The results of the study revealed a significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2, 218}=58.097$; $p<0.05$). However, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students ($F_{2, 218}=0.593$; $p>0.05$) Also There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2, 218}=6.606$; $p>0.05$). It was concluded that the use of teaching aids (charts and models) are effective in enhancing students’ achievement in chemistry. It was recommended among others that, the state ministry of education should provide adequate Charts and Models as instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of Chemistry in Secondary Schools.

Keywords: Teaching aids Charts and models), Achievement and Gender

Introduction

Science education has become a useful tool for National Development. Science education refers to the cultivation and disciplining of an individual to utilize science for improving his/her life, cope with and increasingly technological world or pursue science academically and professionally and for dealing responsibly wit science related social issues (Akpan, 2022). Science education entails the teaching and learning of science process and principles (Basiriyu, 2022). The role of science education in the lives of individuals and in the advancement of science and technology for the development of mankind and the society in general is very crucial (Nalu, 2022). Scientific literacy, which is the gateway to achieve scientific and technological advancement and economic survival, is achievable through science education (Akpan, 2022). The impact of science on a nation and its citizens could be seen from the production of basic human needs to social, political, educational, technological and economic advancement (Manu, 2022). The steps scientists take during scientific investigation (Science processes) and scientific products draw the attention of the society to the fact that science makes life comfortable (Omosona, 2021). According to Aina (2021), Science education is fundamental to technology of any nation of the world. The goals of science education in Nigeria are geared towards the cultivation of inquiring and rational minds for the conduct of a good life and democracy; production of scientists for national development; service studies in technology and the cause of technological development; Provision of knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the form and the conduct of life (Onasanyi, 2021).

Science education comprises of Biology, Chemistry and Physics. According to Omebe (2021) these three subjects are the tripod on which the world's technology rests upon. According to Akpan (2022) chemistry is the study of matter and the changes that matter undergoes. Chemistry is a very important science subject in senior secondary school curricula worldwide. It is a core subject for the medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, and chemical engineering. As important as the chemistry is, and in spite of the efforts of both the federal and state governments to encourage chemistry education, students still shun the subject (Jegade, 2020). Akani (2020) lament that, students' performance in these Chemistry in internal examination is not good enough for the future development of science and technology in Nigeria. Students' mode of response to questions related to organic chemistry is poor. According to West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) chief examiner's report regarding the May/June 2023 WASSCE, majority of the candidates could not correctly write the IUPAC name of organic compounds nor were they able to differentiate between thermal and catalytic cracking. Students' general achievement as reported by WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports on students' performance in the 2019, 2020, 2021 2022, and 2023 examination indicate poor achievement in chemistry. Table 1 below shows the statistics of Katsina State Secondary School Students' achievement Chemistry.

Table 1 Summary of WAEC SSCE Chemistry Result from 2019 - 2023

Year	No. of Students Enrolled									
	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	
2019	38,602	61	72	107	3,330	4,501	3,211	18,341	2,979	6,000
2020	33,720	76	81	98	3,800	3,907	5,607	16,800	1,022	2,329
2021	37,223	68	92	108	2,950	3,201	4,771	13,401	7,502	5,130
2022	39,577	53	68	71	3,107	3,480	5,102	17,807	3,508	6,381
2023	14,513	83	94	107	1,801	2,907	3,101	2,650	1,630	2,140

Source: Department of Planning, Research and Statistics, Katsina State Ministry of Education (2023)

Students' academic performance has been the immediate indicator for the effectiveness of the school system. The planning of the school programme and its objectives are translated in to classroom practices (Mamu, 2022). The effect of the school programme can only be observed in the performance of the students (Baraya, 2022). Unfortunately, the students' performance is not something to talk about as the situation is too worrisome (Baraya, 2022). The underlying evidence to this pitiful situation of poor academic achievement could be traced to the teacher's classroom practices (Mamu, 2022). Omebe and Akani (2020) opined that, science is resource' intensive as such effective teaching of science requires instructional resources. Onasanya and Omosewa (2021) argued that, no matter how well trained or qualified a teacher is, if the school lacks equipment and instructional resources, he will fail to put his ideas into practice.

Instructional materials such as models and charts are suggested for the effective teaching of some topics in chemistry such as matter, structures of elements, compounds and hydrocarbons (Edwards, 2022). Charts and models are visual instructional materials which aid the teaching/learning process by appealing to the sense of vision. Nalu (2022) asserted that, the use of models helps students to learn abstract concepts in chemistry (Jotia, 2020). Obviously, most concepts in chemistry seems to be abstract. Structures of compounds and their properties are mostly described by teachers which often create confusion in the minds of the students. Sometimes, curious students are forced to raise questions as to the reality of the existence of chemistry concepts taught in class. In line with this background, it is deemed necessary to empirically determine the effect of charts and models as instructional materials on students' achievement in organic chemistry while using gender as moderating variable.

Teachers, parents and other stakeholders in Science Education have been worried about the poor Achievement of students in internal examinations (Baraya, 2022). In spite of the important position of Chemistry among other science related disciplines, literature has revealed that, students' achievement in Chemistry at Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been consistently poor (Njoku, 2022). It has been observed that students purposively develop phobia anytime Chemistry is mentioned because they see Chemistry as a difficult subject to learn (matlate, 2020). The struggle to improve students' under achievement in chemistry is imperative because Science and Technology is a gateway to National Development. Chemistry is an important science subject relevant for advanced studies in medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, chemical engineering among others (Mamu, 2022). Students must demonstrate learning of chemistry and score at least a credit pass in WASSCE or NECO SSCE before he/she can be admitted into university to study any of the above-mentioned courses (NFE, 2014). If students' poor achievement in chemistry persists, it will not only affect the future of the students but the nation as a whole (okibia, 2022). The plan to advance science and technology in the country as planned by the Federal Republic of Nigeria will remain a mere dream.

The use of charts and models as instructional materials in teaching and learning situation especially in a chemistry class may play a vital role in increasing chemistry students' academic achievement in Senior Secondary School, hence the study seeks to find out Effect of Using Charts and Models as Instructional Materials on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to find out the:

1. Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Research Questions

1. What is the Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?
2. What is the Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?
3. What are the Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Methodology

The study adopted 3 × 2 pre-test post-test quasi experimental factorial design. The study has three groups; experimental group one (EG₁) was exposed to experimental treatment (X₁) involving the use charts while experimental group two (EG₂) was exposed to experimental treatment (X₂) involving the use of models as teaching aids. The control group (CG) was not treated using any of the two teaching aids. The three groups were taught hydrocarbons concept for the period of six weeks using the same instructional strategy (Demonstration). Pre-test (O₁) were administered before treatment to both experimental and control groups. Intact classes were used in both the sample schools. Post-test (O₂) was administered on the six weeks after treatment. The research design of the study is represented in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Diagrammatic Representation of the Research Design

Where: EG₁ = Experimental group (Charts)

EG₂ = Experimental group (Models)

CG = Control group

X₁ = treatment (with charts)

X₂ = treatment (with Models)

O₁ = Pre-test

O₂ = Post test

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 6,328 (Male, 3100 and Female, 3228) Senior Secondary year II (SSII) chemistry Students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The zone comprises of 25 public Senior Senior Secondary School spread within the three Local Governments namely: Katsina, Kaita and Jibia Local Government areas, respectively.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Three schools were randomly selected for the study through balloting technique. In each school, an intact class comprising of both male and female students were selected. The sample size of the study consists of 218 (Male, 124 and Female, 94) students selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique by balloting system to select the sample schools and purposive sampling technique to select population using an intact class.

Instrumentation

Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used for data collection. CAT is a 20-item, multiple choice questions adopted from previous West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) SSCE questions papers. Items on CAT covers Alkanes, Alkenes and Alkynes which are organic Chemistry in line with the National Chemistry Syllabus for SSII. Table of specification is provided in table 3.3 to ascertain the distribution of items:

Table 2: Table of Specification for CAT

SN	Topics	No of items	Know	Comp.	App.	Total
1	ALKANES	8(40%)	4(20%)	1(5%)	3 (15%)	8
2	ALKENES	5(25%)	3 (15%)	0	2 (10%)	5
3	ALKYNES	7(35%)	5(25%)	1 (5%)	1(5%)	7
TOTAL		20	12	2	6	20

KEY; Know. =Knowledge; Comp. =Comprehension; App.=Application

Validity of the Instrument

To ascertain the validity of the test, the twenty items on CAT was submitted to Chemistry and Science Education experts in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University; in which they examine whether the items are suitable for the selected chemistry concepts in terms of item clarity and cognitive demand. After the validation the observation made by the experts were effected. The final draft was pilot tested in order to determine the reliability index

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS). From the result obtained, reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.64. Hence the instrument is reliable.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The choice for ANCOVA stems from the fact that, ANCOVA assesses the effect of the independent variables (Charts and Models) on the dependent variable (academic achievement) as well check the interaction effect of treatment and moderating variable (gender) while using the pretest result as covariate. The covariate helps to control the equivalency of the group and also reduce error terms in the analysis.

Result

Table 3: ANCOVA of Effect of Treatment (Charts and Models) on Students' Achievement in concept of Hydrocarbon

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Corrected Model	2141.058	6	356.843	56.630	.000	*Sig
Intercept	1154.989	1	1154.989	183.292	.000	*Sig
Pretest	237.886	1	237.886	37.752	.000	*Sig
Treatment	732.178	2	366.089	58.097	.000	*Sig
Gender	3.734	1	3.734	.593	.442	**NS
Treatment*Gender	83.258	2	41.629	6.606	.062	*NS

Error	1329.584	211	6.301
Total	28118.000	218	
Corrected Total	3470.642	217	

a. R Squared = .617 (Adjusted R Squared = .606); *Significant, **Not Significant

Research Question 1

What is the Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 4 : Descriptive Statistics of Experimental and Control Groups Pretest

Group	N	\bar{x}	Stdev	SE
Experiment Group A	77	5.44	1.84	.21
Experiment Group B	72	4.26	1.55	.18
Control Group	69	3.27	.92	.11

N = Numbers of Groups, X = Mean, Stdev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 4, above, the Charts group had a mean pretest score of 5.44 and a standard deviation of 1.84. The models group had a mean pretest score of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 1.55 and the lecture (control) group had a mean pretest score of 3.27 and standard deviation of 0.92. This means that, the three groups performed at different levels.

Research Question 2

What is the Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 5 : Descriptive Statistics of Experimental and Control Groups Posttest Scores

Group	N	\bar{x}	Stdev	SE
Experiment Group A	77	14.11	3.86	.44
Experiment Group B	72	10.34	2.26	.26
Control Group	69	7.04	1.42	.17

N = Numbers of Groups, X = Mean, Stdev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 5, above, the Charts group had a mean posttest score of 14.11 and a standard deviation of 3.86. The models group had a mean posttest score of 10.34 and a standard deviation of 2.26 and the lecture (control) group had a mean posttest score of 7.04 and standard deviation of 1.42. This means that, the three groups performed at different levels.

Research Question 3

What are the Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 6 : Descriptive Statistics of Male and Female students' Posttest Scores

Gender	N	\bar{x}	Stdev	SE	MD
Male	124	10.64	3.92	.35	
Female	94	10.61	4.11	.42	.02

N = Numbers of Groups, \bar{x} = Mean, Stdev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 6, above the posttest, the male students had a mean score of 10.64 and a standard deviation of 3.92 while the female students had a mean score of 10.61 and a standard deviation of 4.11. The mean difference observed in the posttest scores of the students is 0.02. This means that, the male students slightly perform better than the female students.

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁:

There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

In table 3, There is significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2, 218} = 58.097; p < 0.05$). This means that, the treatment is effective in enhancing students' achievement in chemistry. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2

H₀2:

There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students.

In table 3, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students ($F_{1, 218} = 0.593; p > 0.05$). This means that, the treatment is gender friendly. In other word, the treatment applied in this study did not differ on students' gender to be effective. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students is retained.

Hypothesis 3

H₀3:

There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students.

In table 3, there is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students. ($F_{2, 218} = 6.606; p > 0.05$). That is, the treatment does not depend on gender to be effective. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students is retained.

In summary, the main effect of treatment is significant, but the main effect of gender and it interaction effect with treatment on students' achievement are not significant. The coefficient of determination shows that, the treatment accounted for 61.7% of the variation in the students' achievement in chemistry ($R^2 = 0.617$). It is therefore important to determine if any significant difference exist between the groups since different methods were used to treat the groups. Table 5 below shows the univariate test for the difference.

Table 7: Univariate Test of the Group Mean Scores

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Contrast	732.178	2	366.089			
Error	1329.584	211	6.301	58.097	.000	*Sig

*Significance

In table 7, there is significant difference in the mean scores of the three groups ($F_{2, 211} = 58.097; p < 0.05$). This means that, the three groups performed at different levels. The group(s) that produces the difference needs to be revealed. Table 6 below shows the pairwise comparison of the groups.

Table 8: Pairwise Comparison of Chart, Model and Control Groups

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P	Remark
Charts	Models	2.700*	.439	.000	*Sig
	Control	5.350*	.496	.000	*Sig
Models	Charts	-2.700*	.439	.000	*Sig
	Control	2.651*	.446	.000	*Sig
Control	Charts	-5.350*	.496	.000	*Sig
	Control	-2.651*	.446	.000	*Sig

*Significance

In table 8, there is significant difference between charts and model group (Mean Difference = 2.700; $p < 0.05$). There is also significant difference between charts and Control group (Mean Difference = 5.350; $p < 0.05$). There is significant difference between model and Control group (Mean Difference = 2.651; $p < 0.05$). This comparison therefore shows that, Chart and Models groups are responsible for the variation in the students' achievement. Therefore, they are effective in enhancing students' achievement. However, Charts is better than Models in enhancing students' achievement.

Discussion of the Findings

The study reveals that, there is significant main effect of charts on student's Academic Achievement. The use of charts in teaching chemistry concepts elevate student's Academic Achievement in Chemistry. This finding corroborates with numerous previous studies on the effect of charts across various subjects taught in secondary schools. For instance, Nalu (2022) revealed that, charts has a significant effect on Student Academic Achievement in Biology. Basiriyu (2022) state that, there is strong positive correlation between the use of charts with student's academic achievement in chemistry. There is no doubt, that pictorial view of concepts or real objects used in teaching simplifies the teacher job and as well raise the students understanding and achievement in test or examination. Students in the experimental group outperformed their counterpart in the control group because of the advantage of having mental picture of the concept taught via the use of charts.

The study reveals that, there is significant main effect of models on student's Achievement in chemistry. Models have the potential to elevate student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. This finding corroborates with numerous previous studies on the effect of models across various subjects taught in secondary schools. For instance, Enohuan (2020) established a significant effect of model Academic Achievement. Basiriyu (2022) state that, there is a strong positive correlation between instructional materials such as models with student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. There is no doubt that three dimensional objects use in teaching do not only simplifies the teacher job but also raise the students' understanding and Achievement. Students in the experimental group outperformed their counterpart in the control group not because they are naturally ingenious but the advantage of having mental picture of the concept taught via the use of models is what elevate their understanding and subsequently better achievement.

The study also revealed that, gender effect do not impede students' Academic Achievement of chemistry concepts when charts is used. This finding agrees with the findings of Nalu (2022), Basiriyu (2022) and Enohuan (2020), who revealed that, gender effect are not significant in terms of student's Academic Achievement. All things being equal, under normal circumstances, when students are exposed to certain chemistry concepts in the same environment, using appropriate teaching strategy and materials, the students will perform equally without bias. This finding therefore prove that, students can perform equally when charts and models concepts equally irrespective of their gender.

The study further revealed that, gender effect do not impede students' Academic Achievement of chemistry concepts when models is used. This finding agrees with the findings of Momoh (2021), Moronfolo (2021) and Enohuan (2020), who revealed that, gender effect are not significant in terms of student's Academic Achievement. All things being equal, under normal circumstances, when students are exposed to certain chemistry concepts in the same environment, using appropriate teaching strategy and materials, the students will perform equally without bias. This finding therefore prove that, students can perform equally when charts and models concepts equally irrespective of their gender.

The study finally revealed that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment (charts and models) and gender on student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. This study is in line with Okobia (2022) who reported no significant effect of treatment (charts and models) and gender on students' Academic Achievement in chemistry. In addition, Jotia and Matlate (2020) reported non-significant difference in the Achievement scores of students according to treatment (charts and models) and gender. The result showed that student's gender is not a significant factor in student's Achievement in different treatment. This implies that both charts and models effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in chemistry irrespective of students' gender.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be concluded that the use of charts and models as instructional materials are effective in enhancing students' achievement, in other words utilization of charts and models as instructional materials have the potential of enhancing students' academic achievement, irrespective category of gender the students belong. Charts are better than models to enhance students' Academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers and students should not only be encouraged to use chart and models in teaching chemistry concepts, but they should be supervised to ensure they frequently use them in their day-to-day teaching activities.
2. The government and Parents Teachers Association (PTA) should participate in the provision of instructional materials and community resources in schools for effective teaching.
3. State ministry of education should provide adequate Charts and Models as instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools.

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